

Studies on molecular interaction of tetracyclines with adenine – a spectroscopic investigation

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The interaction of tetracycline, terramycin and doxycycline with adenine has been investigated spectroscopically. The interaction is weak and the equilibrium constant values for the above systems at 37° are 25, 7.4 and 24.5 ± 0.2 dm³ mol⁻¹ respectively.

The formation of molecular complexes between electron donors and acceptors has long been recognized as an important phenomenon¹ and the possible importance of charge transfer complexes in biological systems were suggested by Pullaman² as well as by Szent Gyorgyi³, and the role of charge transfer forces are now accepted in biological systems⁴. Many drugs form charge-transfer complexes with chloranil, 1,4-dinitrobenzene, 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene and other well known organic electron-acceptors in a solvent of low dielectric constant. On the other hand, purines, pyrimidines and amino acids undergo charge-transfer complexation with various electron-accepting and electron-donating species⁵ and in all such cases the term receptor is used to denote the site of action of the drug⁶. Some workers feel that a drug acts so long as it is attached to the receptor. In many cases it would appear that the binding of drug to the receptor is relatively weak. Thus in typical pharmacological assays, a drug can be washed out of a preparation and replaced by another drug. Paton's⁷ theory of stimulation demands that the drug-receptor complex shall be capable of dissociation in addition of high rate of association. Chemically this reversible behavior could occur by ionic association through hydrogen bonding or by other forces which might include charge transfer forces, or what is more likely, a combination of several of these types of forces⁸.

As we are interested to know whether the compounds used as drugs, namely antibiotics, do really participate in charge-transfer complexation with DNA or they simply form loose adducts due to van der Waals type of interaction, we have chosen tetracyclines as a representative to study the interaction of antibiotics with adenine, a constituent of DNA.

In addition, being interested in the study of interaction of tetracyclines with adenine, we have used water as solvent (whereas the earlier researchers used low dielectric solvent) and the temperature of the experiment was 37° (body temperature). We thought it may be worthwhile to investigate the effect of pH (as the pH of the medium in

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄
Tetracycline (Achromycin)	H	OH	CH ₃	H
5-Oxytetracycline (Terramycin)	OH	OH	CH ₃	H
6-Deoxy 5-oxy tetracycline(Doxycycline)	OH	H	CH ₃	H

different parts of body liquids are different) and the effect of cation, namely Mg²⁺ on the strength of interaction of drugs with adenine.

Results and Discussion

Tetracyclines, due to their chromophoric groups give rise to characteristic absorption spectra that extend into the visible region. In buffer solutions of pH 7, tetracycline hydrochloride, terramycin hydrochloride and doxycycline hydrochloride absorb at 275 ($\epsilon = 14374$) and 360 (13830); 273 ($\epsilon = 10799$) and 357 (10455) and 273 ($\epsilon = 6589$) and 348 (5441) nm respectively. It is quite interesting to note that when the positions of H and OH (in R₁ and R₂) of tetracycline hydrochloride are interchanged the electronic spectra of antibiotics are considerably affected (275 → 273 nm; 360 → 348 nm) and the extinction coefficient is decreased to about one-fourth. It is to be noted that the ratio of ϵ_I/ϵ_{II} in all the three tetracyclines remains nearly constant, which indicates that the transitions involved in the two bands (of all the tetracyclines studied) seem to be the same. Adenine, a constituent of DNA, has absorption maxima at 260 nm ($\epsilon = 14899$) in buffer of pH 7.

The spectra of tetracyclines and the 'mixed solutions' are shown in Fig. 1. Tetracycline shows a peak at 360 nm in visible region while adenine does not have any absorption in this region. It can be seen from the spectra that the intensities of tetracyclines are affected after the addition of adenine to the solution of tetracycline. As the adenine concentration is increased at a fixed tetracycline concentration, the absorbance of tetracycline hydrochloride at λ_{max} (360

nm) decreases and this is true in the cases of oxytetracycline and doxycycline. The decrease in intensity of the absorption spectra of tetracycline can be attributed to the complex formation of tetracycline with adenine, and due to the interaction the concentration of the uninteracted species decreases and hence the intensity of spectra decreases. From the differential spectra we could locate a new charge-transfer band at ~380 nm. The presence of new band indicates the existence of molecular association between tetracyclines and adenine. Similar observations were made in the case of interaction of antimalarial drugs with DNA and its constituents⁹.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of tetracycline and tetracycline-adenine 'mixed solutions' at 37° (pH 7.0) : (1) tetracycline hydrochloride, (2) tetracycline hydrochloride + adenine.

In order to establish the nature of the complex formation, i.e. whether the complex formation arises from a proton donor-acceptor type of interaction between the constituents, the absorption spectra of tetracyclines were measured in water at different pH (4.0, 9.2 and 7.0) (Table 1). As pH of the solution is changed from 4.0 to 9.2, the absorption maximum of tetracycline hydrochloride shifts from 356 to 375 nm (red-shift). The intensities of the

Table 1. Effect of pH on the absorption spectra of tetracyclines at 37°

System	pH 4.0		pH 7.0		pH 9.2	
	λ_{max} nm	ϵ $dm^3 mol^{-1} m^{-1}$	λ_{max} nm	ϵ $dm^3 mol^{-1} m^{-1}$	λ_{max} nm	ϵ $dm^3 mol^{-1} m^{-1}$
Tetracycline	355	1550	360	1383	375	1878
Terramycin	355	1154	357	1045	375	1394
Doxycycline	345	514	348	544	370	901

*Error limit : $\lambda_{max} = \pm 1$ nm, $\epsilon = \pm 20$ $dm^3 mol^{-1} m^{-1}$.

bands in acidic/alkaline medium increase in visible region. Similar trends were observed in the other two tetracyclines. However, with the limited data, it is not possible to generalize the findings.

A Benesi-Hildebrand¹⁰ plot for tetracycline + adenine mixture in water (pH 7.0) gave a good straight-line (Fig. 2), indicating the presence of 1 : 1 molecular adduct. The equilibrium constants at 37° for the interaction between the above mentioned tetracyclines with adenine are 25, 7.4 and 24.5 ± 0.2 $dm^3 mol^{-1}$ respectively (Table 2). So from the present data, it is clear that the interaction is weak and the strength of interaction vary in the order : tetracycline + adenine \cong doxycycline + adenine > terramycin + adenine.

Fig. 2. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for tetracycline-adenine 'mixed system' at 37°; solvent : water (pH 7.0).

It has been reported in the literature that Mg^{2+} ion is essential for the body. Therefore, we thought it may be worthwhile to study the effect of Mg^{2+} on the interaction of tetracyclines with adenine. When Mg^{2+} , in the form of $MgSO_4$ (2 mg in 10 ml), was added to tetracycline hydrochloride, the absorption of tetracycline hydrochloride (4.64×10^{-6} M) increased from 0.642 to 0.670 (increase 0.028) and the band position shifted from 360 to 365 nm. But when 2 mg Mg^{2+} (in 10 ml) was added to a solution of 10 ml of mixture of tetracycline hydrochloride (4.64×10^{-6} M) and adenine (2.76×10^{-3} M) the intensity increased from 0.610 to 0.650 (i.e. 0.040). A new band with $\lambda_{max} \cong 385 \pm 2$ nm appeared having an isosbestic point at $356 \pm$

Table 2. Equilibrium constants data for the tetracyclines-adenine mixed systems at 37°

Solvent : Water (pH 7.0)	K_c M^{-1}	ϵ_{CT} $dm^3 mol^{-1} m^{-1}$
Tetracycline hydrochloride -Adenine	25	13417
Terramycin hydrochloride -Adenine	7.4	10050
Doxycycline hydrochloride -Adenine	24.5	5308

*Error limit : $K_c = \pm 0.4$, $\epsilon_{CT} = \pm 20$ $dm^3 mol^{-1} m^{-1}$.

0.5 nm. This indicates that Mg^{2+} and tetracycline interact with each other and the adduct formed has an absorption band at λ_{max} 385 nm. Similar trends were noticed in the other two cases. These observations go in parallel with that made by Kaazino and Kamiyama¹¹ on the effect of Mg^{2+} on the melting of DNA-mythromycin. From the present investigations it appears as if tetracyclines form complexes with divalent cation like Mg^{2+} .

Thus it appears that tetracyclines interact with adenine, a constituent of DNA and the interaction is weak, and the present results infer that in the presence of Mg^{2+} the interaction between tetracyclines and adenine is slightly stronger, may be due to electrostatic interaction.

Experimental

Tetracyclines, namely, tetracycline hydrochloride, 5-oxytetracycline hydrochloride and 6-deoxy-5-oxytetracycline hydrochloride were used after recrystallization. Adenine was recrystallized from hot water. Buffer solutions of 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2 pH were used as solvents. $MgSO_4$ (B.D.H., A.R.) was used as such. A standard solution of tetracyclines/adenine was prepared in buffer solution. The stock solution was further diluted to the final concentration of the drugs (acceptor) $\sim 10^{-6}$ mol dm^{-3} and that of adenine (donor) $\sim 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} .

The spectra were recorded using a Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer fitted with thermostated cell of 1 cm path – length. All the experiments were carried out at 37°. The spectra of tetracyclines/adenine in buffer solutions were recorded using water as reference (at different pH), while for obtaining the spectra of the mixed solutions a solution of the same strength of adenine used in the ‘mixed solution’ was used as the reference. Spectra of ‘mixed solutions’ of tetracycline hydrochloride-adenine (at pH 7.0)

were recorded, and to these solutions, a known amount of Mg^{2+} (in the form of $MgSO_4$) was added and the spectra were recorded again to see the effect of Mg^{2+} on the interaction of tetracyclines with adenine.

The equilibrium constants were calculated from the slope and intercept of the plots using the relation¹⁰,

$$[A]l/\text{Absorbance}_{\text{complex}} = 1/K\epsilon_c(1/[D]) + 1/\epsilon_c$$

where, l is the optical path - length, $[A]$ and $[D]$ are the initial concentrations of the acceptor and donor respectively, and K and ϵ_c the equilibrium constant and extinction coefficient of the complexes respectively.

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